

FACTORS OF INCREASING LABOR EFFICIENCY AND FACTORS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Annotation. The article contains opinions related to increasing economic efficiency and ensuring economic growth. Ways, factors and means of achieving economic efficiency are analyzed.

Key words: economy, effective labor, labor productivity, investment, social production, money, production.

The issue of labor efficiency and economic development has been of interest to scientists in every period of human society. This issue has become one of the most urgent issues in the 21st century, and it has become a topic of interest for philosophers as well as economists. Because the occurrence of fundamental changes in the modern economy, the acceleration of integration processes in the world economy, and the multifaceted importance of international economic relations have a noticeable effect on this process.

In the conditions of constantly developing market relations, the correct organization of labor in the enterprise should ensure the reproduction of the labor force, the formation of motivation and incentives for labor, and the increase of its quality and labor productivity. At the present scale of production, when live labor is more and more involved in it, the saving of total production labor costs is of particular economic importance in ensuring an increase in the volume of production. Increasing labor productivity is becoming one of the main sources of economic growth. Increasing the productivity of live labor is based on increasing its technical equipment, expanding and improving machine systems. The higher the quality of the means of production, the more labor products the worker creates. It should be noted that each individual enterprise has a certain level of labor productivity.

The level of labor productivity can increase or decrease under the influence of various factors. The growth of labor productivity plays an important role in the development of production. It represents a general economic law and is an economic necessity for the development of society, regardless of which economic system prevails.

It is not enough to answer the question of how the working group worked in the current economic conditions. First of all, it is necessary to determine what changes occurred in labor during the production process. These changes can be both positive and negative.

Improving labor productivity is important both for the organization and for society as a whole. It contributes to:

1. Increasing the volume of production in the organization.
2. Reduction of production costs (semi-fixed costs are reduced) and, as a result, increase the profit of the organization and improve the financial condition of the organization.
3. Development of production, renewal of product types.
4. To increase the income of the organization's employees and increase their material well-being.
5. An increase in the state's national income, which in turn leads to the state's allocation of more funds for economic development and social needs of the population.

The most common and universal indicator of labor productivity is production. In industrial enterprises, there are 3 main methods of measuring labor productivity based on the unit of measurement of production volume:

1. Natural - physically describes production per unit of work time (kilograms, meters, pieces, etc.).
2. Price - has become widely used due to the fact that it allows to calculate and compare different types of work by bringing them to a common counter. In the conditions of high inflation, the criterion of the cost of production produces incomparable labor results. To avoid the influence of the value factor, complex recalculations must be performed. In addition, the value of the production indicator is affected by:
 - material consumption of products, cost of used raw materials.
 - changes in the composition of manufactured products and the share of cooperative supply.
 - differences in the level of profitability of different types of products.
3. Labor - describes the ratio of standard costs to actual working hours (hours, standard hours).

Labor productivity is an indicator of the economic efficiency of the work of employees. The concept of labor efficiency is broader than the concept of productivity, and it includes not only economic aspects (in fact, labor productivity), but also psychophysiological and social aspects. If the following requirements are not met, the rate of growth of labor productivity will inevitably decrease: - poor sanitation - working conditions harmful to hygiene and human health; - useless waste of working time due to illness; -reduction of the most active period of human labor; - granting additional vacations, etc.

In the conditions of the market economy, it is much more important to calculate productivity by the volume of products sold, because the increase in unfinished production and the accumulation of unsold product residues do not have a positive economic value. Many factors affect the level of labor productivity and its dynamics. Factors are driving forces and reasons that influence changes in labor productivity. Some of them contribute to the increase of labor productivity, while others can cause a decrease in productivity: The first group of factors includes the increase in labor productivity, the organization of work and production, the improvement of the social conditions of workers, the second group is the adverse effect of natural conditions, the organization of production and work lack of achievement, bad influence of negative elements in social conditions.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of 28.01.2022 on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, www.lex.uz
2. Ahunova, M. K. (2021). Use of investment in the development of the national economy. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 10(3), 232-236.
3. Akhunova, M. R. Kh. (2022). Women's entrepreneurship in the innovation economy: problems and solutions. *International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Research*, 2(1), 7-14.
4. Nabiyevna, T. O. (2021). Economic potential of enterprises and its essence. *Academicia Globe: Interscience Research*, 2(6), 49-53.